

1.1 Title

Review and gap analysis of research ethics and integrity frameworks/guidelines addressing environmental and climate concerns in research and innovation

1.2 Authors

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1.3 History of changes

Document Title	Version	Date	Changes
RE4GREEN T1.4 Study Protocol v1.0	1.0	31/10/2024	Initial version of the study protocol.
RE4GREEN T1.4 Study Protocol v1.1	1.1	15/12/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Removed the 10-year mark inclusion criterion.- Added a dedicated research step in the "Identification of RE&RI Guidelines/Frameworks" section.- Updated assessment criteria to also include relevant considerations from Tasks 1.1 and 1.2.- Removed the inclusivity and adaptability assessment criteria

1.4 Introduction

The European Green Deal (EGD) aims to achieve a just and inclusive green transition across Europe. This requires research and innovation (R&I) to align with principles of environmental sustainability and climate responsibility. To ensure that research processes and outcomes adhere to these principles, comprehensive research ethics and integrity (RE&RI) frameworks that explicitly address environmental and climate-related challenges are needed.

Existing RE&RI guidelines, such as the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (ECOC) and other institutional frameworks, provide foundational principles but may not fully encompass the complexities of environmental and climate ethics. To support the green transition, it is critical to review these frameworks, assess their adequacy, and identify gaps where further development or adaptation is needed.

This study aims to systematically identify and assess current RE&RI frameworks and guidelines with a focus on their ability to address environmental and climate concerns in R&I. The findings will inform the development of enhanced or new guidelines as part of task 3.2 in the RE4GREEN project.

1.5 Research question and objectives

Research question: How well do existing RE&RI frameworks and guidelines address environmental and climate concerns in the context of R&I, and what gaps need to be addressed?

Objectives:

1. Compile a detailed list of frameworks and guidelines that address environmental and climate concerns in the context of research ethics and integrity.
2. Assess the relevance and comprehensiveness of these guidelines and frameworks with regard to climate or environmental concerns in R&I, using clearly defined criteria that align with the goals of the RE4GREEN project.
3. Identify where these frameworks fall short in addressing environmental and climate ethics and recommend areas for improvement or the creation of new guidelines.

2.1 Identification and Initial Screening of Frameworks/Guidelines

Step 1: Definition of inclusion criteria

Objective: Establish clear inclusion criteria to guide the identification and selection of relevant research ethics and integrity frameworks/guidelines that address environmental and climate concerns in R&I:

Relevance: The documents must primarily focus on research ethics and integrity.

Geographical scope: The documents must be applicable within the European Research Area (ERA) or recognised by international bodies influencing European research practices. Additionally, global guidelines were considered if they were widely adopted or referenced within the ERA.

Type of document: Grey literature, including RE&RI guidelines, frameworks, codes of conduct, and institutional frameworks, was included, along with certain relevant research publications. Training materials, tools, and resources (reviewed under Task 1.3) were excluded.

Purpose: Documents needed to provide guidance on ethics and integrity in R&I.

Target audience: Frameworks and guidelines targeting researchers, policymakers, ethics experts and reviewers, citizen scientists, funders, integrity officers, innovators, students, publishers, and editors were included.

Language accessibility: Documents needed to be discoverable through English-language search queries. Once found, non-English documents were considered if they could be translated into English.

Step 2: Identification of RE&RI Guidelines/Frameworks

I. Research from previous EU projects

We will leverage findings from past EU-funded projects to identify existing RE&RI frameworks/guidelines relevant to environmental and climate concerns in R&I, also utilising the recently published Ethics and Integrity results pack by the European Commission (EC)¹.

II. Literature review from task 1.1

We will leverage the systematic literature review conducted in Task 1.1 to identify relevant research ethics and integrity frameworks/guidelines focusing specifically

¹ Ethics and integrity: Building bridges for trust and excellence in research and innovation, <https://cordis.europa.eu/article/id/450170-ethics-and-integrity-building-bridges-for-trust-and-excellence-in-research-and-innovation>

on the literature tagged with “Research ethics and integrity guidelines” within the Covidence platform.

III. Guidelines/frameworks used by consortium or SAB members

We will collect existing RE&RI frameworks/guidelines used by institutions within the consortium and the Stakeholder Advisory Board (SAB).

IV. Literature review

We will utilise the detailed search and findings² identified by VUMC according to their research protocol³.

V. Dedicated research efforts

Finally, to further ensure the completeness of our dataset, we will conduct an independent and targeted search for additional guidelines and frameworks, minimising the risk of omitting critical resources. We will use platforms such as Google and The Embassy of Good Science (2022), and search terms will include combinations of keywords such as “research ethics guidelines,” “research integrity frameworks,” “ethics and integrity in research,” and “guidelines for responsible innovation.”

Based on findings from I-V, we will compile a comprehensive list of guidelines/frameworks and conduct an initial screening using the inclusion criteria outlined in Step 1.

2.2 Assessment of Frameworks/Guidelines

Step 3: Assessment criteria

Objective: Create a set of criteria to assess the selected frameworks/guidelines. The assessment criteria are designed to incorporate specific ethical, theoretical, and practical considerations identified in Tasks 1.1 and 1.2. The following criteria will be used to evaluate each framework/guideline:

References and relevance to environmental/climate ethics: Does the framework/guideline explicitly address issues such as sustainability, climate justice, and the “do no significant harm” principle? To evaluate this, we will review in detail each document and conduct a keyword search within each document using terms related to environmental ethics and climate responsibility (*sustainability, environmental/climate justice, precautionary principle, carbon neutrality, environmental/climatic ethics, environmental/climatic impact, green transition, environmental/climatic responsibility, environment/climate responsibility, do no significant harm, European Green Deal, net zero*)

Comprehensiveness: Does the framework/guideline cover a wide range of environmental and climate ethics aspects relevant to R&I, as identified in T1.1 and T1.2?

- Specific ethical or theoretical concepts including but not limited to risk (systemic, environmental), justice (distributive, harm-avoidance, epistemic, participatory, recognition, intergenerational, environmental,

² Claudia Pallise Perello, Krishma Labib, and Natalie Evans: Research Protocol - What do research integrity and open science codes and guidelines mean for research fairness?: A scoping review, <https://osf.io/8chtj>

³ Claudia Pallise Perello, Krishma Labib, and Natalie Evans: Findings - What do research integrity and open science codes and guidelines mean for research fairness?: A scoping review, <https://osf.io/mgsrk>

non-ideal, energy, etc), sustainability (strong, weak), responsibility, ecomodernism, ecofeminism.

- Specific principles including but not limited to the precautionary principle, leave no one behind, polluter-pays, beneficiary-pays, compensation/rectification, informed consent.
- Domains of technology/research/innovation including but not limited to coverage of geoengineering, digital, transportation, agricultural, gene editing, energy and nano technologies.
- Environmental issues including but not limited to climate change, pollution, biodiversity loss, waste, ozone depletion.

Step 4: Frameworks/Guidelines assessment

Objective: Systematically assess each identified framework/guideline using the developed criteria.

We will use a standardised assessment tool (e.g., a review matrix) customised to these criteria to evaluate each framework/guideline.

We will perform a comparative analysis to determine which frameworks/guidelines are most effective in addressing environmental and climate ethics.

We will identify gaps in the existing frameworks/guidelines where environmental and climate ethics are inadequately addressed and provide recommendations for the enhancement of existing or the development of new guidelines/frameworks.

3.1 Expected Outputs

1. Comprehensive list of identified research ethics and integrity frameworks/guidelines.
2. Assessments for each framework/guideline.
3. Gap analysis identifying areas for improvement in existing frameworks/guidelines.
4. Final report summarising findings and recommendations to be then utilised in Task 3.2 (Produce and/or adapt operational ethics and integrity guidelines).